

PROCESSING OF HIGH PERFORMANCE BIOCOMPOSITES FOR THE USE IN THE EUROPEAN BUILDING INDUSTRY

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Keywords: Biocomposites, natural fibers, polyfurfuryl alcohol resin, NFRPC-sandwich, cork

ABSTRACT

In recent years, natural fiber reinforced polymer composites (NFRPC) have gained much attention, both by academia and industry, due to their lightweight potential, low density, environmental performance and economic benefits. The main application area for these materials is in automotive semi-structural interior parts. In order to expand the application area of NFRPC it is important to improve their performance. Therefore, the aim of this work is the material development as well as the investigation and optimization of the processing of biocomposites made of flax and jute textiles with bio-based polyfurfuryl alcohol resin (PFA). By optimizing the manufacturing process and using aligned fibers instead of conventional non-wovens, the mechanical as well as physical performance of these bio-composites could be significantly increased in comparison to standard NFRPC. Thus, the developed materials are suitable for the use in structural applications, for example in the building industry.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to environmental legislation and improved possibilities for insulation, the direct building energy (used for heating) has dropped 6-fold in Europe in the last decades. In contrast, the indirect, embodied building energy has increased slightly over the same period [1]. This energy is mainly caused by the choice of applied building materials. Conventional composites, such as glass fiber reinforced polymers, offer an alternative solution since they have lower embodied energy than many of the traditional building materials like aluminum and bricks. However, biocomposites made of natural fibers and a bio-based resin offer an even lower embodied energy [2]. By substituting traditionally used building materials with biocomposite materials, 50 % reduction of embodied energy is expected for several new building products [3].

Natural fiber reinforced polymer composites have been applied in the European automotive industry for decades due to their environmental and economic benefits [4]. For automotive applications, the natural fibers are first processed to non-woven mats, afterwards impregnated with a polymer and then processed to finished parts. Due to the randomly oriented fibers, the usage of these NFRPC is restricted to semi-structural parts like door panels or seat backs. To expand the application area of biocomposites to structural components in the building industry, it is important to improve their mechanical as well as physical performance. The mechanical performance mainly depends on the orientation of the reinforcing fiber in the composite material. Hence, the general basis for producing structural composite materials is the application of endless aligned fibers, which are woven to textiles.

Furthermore, the mechanical as well as physical properties of NFRPC are also directly correlated with their density. In fact, a higher density leads to higher part stiffness and less water absorption of the composites [5]. On this account, the optimization of the manufacturing process is a further major step towards increasing the density and performance of the biocomposites.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Natural fiber fabrics made of flax (2x2 twill, area weight 420 g/m²) and jute (plain weave, area weight 240 g/m²) yarns were supplied by Composites Evolution, United Kingdom. The bi-directional

alignment of the natural fiber yarns in the fabrics leads to non-isotropic behavior of the composite, but the stiffness in both fiber directions is elevated compared to non-woven materials.

The thermoset bio-based polyfurfuryl alcohol resin (PFA) supplied by TransFurans Chemicals, Belgium, was used as matrix material. So far, PFA resin was mainly known in foundry engineering as binder for sand due to its non-flammability, and was considered as eco-friendly and harmless alternative to formaldehyde resins [6]. It is gained from the waste of the sugar industry, so-called bagasse, and, therefore, it is not in competition with the food industry. It cures under elevated temperature ($> 140\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) by a polycondensation reaction in which water steam is produced.

For applications in which the materials are subjected to high bending loads, the bending stiffness can be increased by the production of a bio-sandwich composite, using cork granule (waste product of cork stoppers manufacturing) for the core. Cork is a very versatile natural raw material. It is very lightweight, elastic, flexible and impermeable to gases or liquids [7]. In this case, the natural fiber reinforced PFA resin is used as a thin skin layer which absorbs tensile and compression forces, the core absorbs thrust forces and preserves the skin layers from deformation. Different core thicknesses were supplied by Amorim Cork Composites, Portugal.

2.1 Textile impregnation

The basis for the manufacture of natural fiber PFA (NF/PFA) composites is the production of pre-pregs, semi-finished pre-impregnated fabrics, which can be processed by a further compression molding technique. PFA resin is supplied as a solution in water. The natural fiber textiles are impregnated by dipping into this resin solution. Excess resin is removed by running the fabrics through foulard rollers with a defined gap, which can be varied to control the amount of resin pick-up. The pre-preg is then partially cured in a convection air oven in order to simplify the handling and pre-dry the pre-preg. The main challenge during textile impregnation is to ensure that fiber weight fraction as well as resin flow are high enough, while the pre-preg is sufficiently pre-dried. The highest natural fiber contents in composites manufacturing could be achieved with approx. 50 wt.-% flax fabric (50 wt.-% PFA) and approx. 38 wt.-% jute fabric (62 wt.-% PFA) fraction in the pre-pregs. The difference in fiber weight fractions of the pre-pregs can be explained by the different kinds of used fabrics (twill and plain weave) and hence, a different impregnation behavior of both fabrics. However, the difference in weight fractions could also be a result of different natural fiber types, since their variety in constituents could affect the fiber-matrix-adhesion and therefore also the fiber weight fraction. It could be observed in previous works that the optimum fiber weight fraction for jute 2x2 twill textiles is also lower than of the same flax twill textile. This confirms the second statement with different fiber types.

2.2 Composite and bio-sandwich manufacturing

The processing of pre-pregs to composites is performed by using hot press technique, which is also the most common technique for processing thermoset NFRPC in the automotive industry [8]. In order to compare the properties of flax/PFA and jute/PFA composites an equal area weight of 1800 g/m^2 was aimed at. Due to the different area weights of the fabrics and fiber weight fractions in the pre-pregs the resulting area weight could be achieved by stacking 2 layers of flax pre-preg or 3 layers of jute pre-preg and placing the stacks into a heated tool during processing.

PFA resin cures at relatively low, for natural fibers suitable temperatures of about $155\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at a pressure of 10 bar. The water steam, which is caused by the water content in the resin and additionally by the polycondensation reaction, could lead to undesirable delamination or porosity in the composite. In order to avoid this, the pressing tool is lifted repeatedly to release the water steam. The pressing time under laboratory conditions is 370 s and can be optimized for industrial applications by using an open tool which reduces the ventilation cycles. The process parameters for the production of NF/PFA composites (here: panels) are shown schematically in Figure 1 (a). The resulting composite panel characteristics for flax/PFA and jute/PFA are shown in Table 1. The density was determined by a volumetric calculation, provided that the density of flax and jute fibers is 1.5 g/cm^3 and the density of PFA resin 1.334 g/cm^3 . In a previous work it could be shown that the volumetric calculation of the

NF/PFA density and volume fractions shows good correlation with other determination methods like μ CT [5].

Material	Area Weight g/m ²	Density g/cm ³	Fiber weight fraction Wt.-%	Fiber volume fraction Vol.-%
Flax/PFA	1800 ± 36	1.28 ± 0.04	46.49 ± 0.01	40.08 ± 0.00
Jute/PFA	1877 ± 34	1.29 ± 0.03	36.08 ± 0.02	33.04 ± 0.02

Table 1: Characteristics of manufactured composite panels

The production of bio-sandwiches with cork composite as core material is analogous to the production of biocomposite panels in the hot press technique. In this process 2 layers of flax/PFA prepreg (2x2 twill) at each side of the cork composite are forming the cover layers. Flax was used because the pre-pregs have a higher fiber content than jute pre-pregs. For the processing, the parameters are adjusted. Due to the low density of the cork core (0.25 g/cm³) a high amount of air is entrapped in the microstructure of the cork granules. This air expands at high temperatures and, in addition, the applied pressure of 10 bar increases the boiling point of the water produced by PFA curing. Even if this water is still liquid at a temperature of 155 °C, it will expand as water steam at the end of the process when the pressure is released. This could lead to a delamination between the core and the skin layers. On that account, the cork sandwiches are cooled under pressure in the production process. This extends the process time to 2100 s in lab-scale, Figure 1 (b). Eight flax/PFA sandwich panels with 5 mm, 6 mm and 10 mm core and a reference panel with the same process parameters and same layer stack (without cork core) were produced. The 5 mm cork was pre-dried for two panels in order to investigate the impact of pre-drying and water content in the cork. The weight loss after drying was 3.1 % for 5 mm cork core. The resulting sandwich panel characteristics are shown in Table 2.

Figure 1: Process parameters for the manufacture of
a) NF/PFA composites and b) NF/PFA sandwiches with cork core

Panel no.	Prepreg layers	Cork thickness mm	Area weight g/m ²	Density g/cm ³	Remarks
1	2 + 2	5	4937 ± 36	0.98 ± 0.01	Cork dried
2	2 + 2	5	4813 ± 63	0.94 ± 0.02	
3	2 + 2	5	4634 ± 56	1.01 ± 0.02	Cork dried
4	2 + 2	5	4922 ± 43	0.90 ± 0.03	
5	2 + 2	6	4831 ± 40	0.95 ± 0.02	
6	2 + 2	6	4867 ± 43	0.93 ± 0.02	
7	2 + 2	10	6118 ± 110	0.77 ± 0.02	
8	2 + 2	10	5862 ± 61	0.80 ± 0.02	
Reference	2 + 2	x	3650 ± 39	1.37 ± 0.01	No cork

Table 2: Characteristics of manufactured bio-sandwiches

2.3 Description of mechanical testing

In order to investigate the mechanical performance of NF/PFA composites manufactured by compression molding, tensile and bending tests were performed according to DIN EN ISO 527-4 and DIN EN ISO 178 on a standard hydraulic testing machine at a displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min for both tests. As usual for long fiber reinforced polymers, unnotched specimens (type 2) with a width of 25 mm were tested. At least five specimens were measured. The clamping length of tensile specimens was 150 mm, the span L for bending tests depends on the thickness h of the material and was $L = 16 \cdot h$.

In order to calculate Young's modulus correctly, the displacement during tensile tests was measured by an extensometer with a gauge length of 50 mm in a range between 0.05 and 0.25 % strain. Since the tensile behavior of NFRPC shows two regions, due to the yield point of natural fibers at room temperature, the slope of the stress-strain diagram might be nonlinear in this region [9, 10]. Therefore, the modulus was also calculated using the slope of the stress-strain diagram in the range of 10 % and 40 % of maximum force (according to DIN EN 310 for wood-based panels). The bending modulus was also calculated between 0.05-0.25 % strain and additionally between 10-40 % maximum force.

For the examination of the strength and deformability of sandwich components subjected to bending loads, a 4-point bending test was performed according to DIN 53293. Unlike the 3-point bending tests with a bending load at one point, the specimens during the 4-point bending test are loaded at two points with two bending dies. This causes pure bending and a constant bending moment between the points of load, whereas shear forces and bending moments are induced between the bending dies and supports. The test setup is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2: Test setup of a 4-point bending test with sandwich specimen [11]

The tests were performed on a standard hydraulic testing machine, which is able to measure the traverse path f_s , which means the distance of the points of load. It is expected that the deflection in the middle of the specimen f_m is higher than f_s , therefore the maximum deflection of the specimen center f_m was determined optically by using an image analysis. The used camera recorded 7.5 images per second, which could be analyzed by the software Motion Studio. By using a displacement rate of 5 mm/min all specimens failed between 60 and 180 seconds. The sandwich structures can be compared by the bending stiffness of the material, which is usually calculated by the product of Young's modulus E and moment of inertia J . Here, the effective bending stiffness $(E \cdot J)_{eff}$ can be calculated by only using the test results of the 4-point bending test, which are force F , span L_A , deflection of specimen center f_m , deflection of support f_s . The effective bending stiffness can be calculated according to equation (1).

$$(E \cdot J)_{eff} = \frac{F \cdot L_A^3}{256 (f_m - f_s)} \quad (1)$$

2.4 Description of water exposure tests

In order to test the applicability of the developed NF/PFA composites and bio-sandwiches as outdoor cladding, the materials were tested in a long-term water exposure trial. For this purpose, square test specimens with an edge length of 61 mm were stored in demineralized water at 23 ± 2 °C according to DIN EN ISO 62 and their weight was measured at fixed intervals according to DIN EN 2378. The trial was stopped after 2184 hours (91 days). The water uptake c was calculated according to equation (2), whereas m_1 is the initial weight before water exposure and m_2 the weight of the specimen after a defined interval.

$$c = \frac{m_2 - m_1}{m_1} \cdot 100 \% \quad (2)$$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical performance of NF/PFA composites

For the investigation of differences between moduli calculated in a range of the slope of 0.05-0.25 % strain and 10-40 % maximum force, three exemplary composite panels made of flax/PFA and jute/PFA each have been compared. The results of differences in Young's modulus calculated by strain E_{str}^t and modulus calculated by maximum force E_F^t are shown in Figure 3 a). It can be observed that E_F^t for flax/PFA is slightly higher than E_{str}^t and the difference lies within the range of the standard deviation. For jute/PFA their E_F^t is up to 1 GPa higher than E_{str}^t . The same behavior can be observed for the flexural modulus calculated by strain E_{str}^b and by maximum force E_F^b . For flax/PFA E_{str}^b and E_F^b lie within the same range (see Figure 3 b). The standard deviation for E_F^b is slightly lower, which shows that the force calculation method provides more reproducible results. For jute/PFA E_F^b is significantly higher (up to 1.2 GPa) than E_{str}^b , whereas the standard deviation lies within the same range.

Figure 3: Comparison of different calculation methods for
a) Young's modulus and b) bending modulus

Both figures show that the mechanical performance of flax/PFA is slightly higher than of jute/PFA which can be explained by the higher fiber weight content in flax/PFA composites. However, many hypotheses have been made in literature to explain the nonlinear behavior of natural fibers during mechanical load. On this basis, the differences between flax and jute behavior can be explained by different tilt angles of the cellulose fibrils which decrease under load. Since in this work aligned fibers in form of textiles are used and thus, the fibers are oriented towards the load direction, other reasons could be a reorganization of the cell structure in the direction of the fiber axis with an increase in length of the fibrils [10]. These differences between flax and jute based composites with the same matrix system could also be explained by the fabric type. For the production of bi-directional textiles like twill and plain weave, the fibers were first manufactured to yarns with a defined twist angle. The

twist during yarn production could also induce a modification of the cell wall structure which leads to different microfibril twisting angles of both, the flax and jute fibers. These microfibril angles can have an influence on the shear strain and tensile behavior [9].

On the basis of these observations, the Young's as well as flexural modulus for all other samples were calculated in the range of the slope between 10-40 % maximum force. Thus, in the following, E_F^t and E_F^b are both designated only as Young's or flexural modulus without mentioning the calculation method.

The tensile stiffness and strength of compression molded NF/PFA composites with flax and jute textile is shown in Figure 4 a) and b) in comparison to standard natural fiber polypropylene (NF/PP) with 50 % fiber weight content and a density of approx. 0.84 g/cm³ and standard natural fiber thermoset (NF/TS) materials with 65 % fiber weight content and a density of 0.80 g/cm³. Both reference materials are commonly used in the European automotive industry. The error bars represent the dispersion of values due to different manufacturers, a variety in density, fiber content and type, and in case of NF/TS different polymer matrices. Usually, NF/TS have higher mechanical properties than NF/PP materials because of better fiber-matrix adhesion of thermoset resins with natural fibers and, therefore, also a higher fiber weight fraction. For the sake of completeness, the NF/PP material properties are shown in the following diagrams, but the comparison of the developed bio-materials will only be performed with NF/TS, because the matrix of the biocomposites is also a thermoset resin.

The Young's modulus of NF/TS is between 3.5 GPa and 5.5 GPa. Although the fiber weight contents of flax/PFA and jute/PFA are 47 %, respectively 36 %, and thus lower than in conventional NF/TS materials, the modulus of jute/PFA is approx. 8.5 GPa and the modulus of flax/PFA is approx. 10 GPa. Thus, an increased modulus of 120 % compared to standard NF/TS can be observed. The tensile strength of the latter is 30-50 MPa. The strength of jute/PFA lies well within the same range as the stress of NF/TS with 42 MPa, whereas the strength of flax/PFA is 57 MPa and is therefore 43 % higher than the strength of standard NF/TS.

Figure 4: Tensile stiffness (a) and tensile strength (b) of NF/PFA composites compared to standard natural fiber polymers commonly used in the automotive industry

The flexural modulus and flexural stress of NF/PFA composites with flax and jute textile is shown in Figure 5 a) and b) in comparison to standard natural fiber materials. The flexural modulus of NF/TS is usually between 3.7-4.9 GPa. The modulus of jute/PFA is approx. 6.8 GPa and of flax/PFA 8.4 GPa. Here again, a significantly increased modulus of 95 % can be observed compared to NF/TS. The flexural stress of NF/TS is usually 50-80 MPa. A high increase of the flexural stress can be observed in the NF/PFA composites. With 88 MPa stress for jute and 130 MPa for flax the stress is up to 30-100 % higher than in standard NF/TS materials.

Figure 5: Flexural Modulus (a) and flexural stress (b) of NF/PFA composites compared to standard natural fiber polymers commonly used in the automotive industry

3.2 Mechanical performance of NF/PFA sandwiches

The high mechanical properties of NF/PFA composites can be further increased by combining the developed material with cork composites. In this context, three different cork thicknesses have been investigated: 5 mm, 5 mm dried (preconditioned), 6 mm, and 10 mm (see also Table 2). The effective bending stiffness is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Effective bending stiffness of flax/PFA bio-sandwiches compared to flax/PFA composite

It can be observed that the cork core has a major impact on the stiffness of the sandwich material, which increases with increasing core thickness. The stiffness for 5 mm and 6 mm cores lies well within the same range and about 100 % higher than the stiffness of the reference biocomposite. It is at first sight unexpected that the dried 5 mm core material leads to a slightly lower stiffness than the unconditioned 5 mm core. A reason for this behavior could be the pretreatment at elevated temperatures, which causes a collapse of the cork composite. The higher density of pre-dried sandwich materials (see Table 2) confirms this statement.

For a very high bending load, the stiffness of bio-sandwiches can be increased even more with a thicker core. By doubling the core thickness to 10 mm, the stiffness can be increased eightfold. The improvement of the stiffness does not follow a linear principle; it is therefore 800 % higher than the stiffness of the reference material.

The results lead to the conclusion that a certain thickness is necessary to gain a significant advantage by using cork as core material.

3.3 Water uptake of NF/PFA composites and cork sandwiches

The water uptake of flax/PFA bio-sandwiches with different core thicknesses and a reference flax/PFA composite without core is shown in Figure 7 a) for the first 24 hours and b) for 13 weeks.

Figure 7: Water uptake of flax/PFA bio-sandwiches after a) 24 hours and b) 2184 hours

It can be observed that water uptake is approx. 3.5 % in the first 24 hours for all bio-sandwiches and 2.8 % for the reference material. In contrast to the NF/PFA composites, the standard NFRPC materials used in the European automotive industry are more permeable to water due to their low density of about 0.8-0.9 g/cm³. Their water uptake is about 13.5 % for natural fiber reinforced thermoset polymer [12] and up to 30 % for natural fiber reinforced polypropylene [13]. In Figure 7 b) it can be observed that the cork core has no significant influence on the water uptake in the first 300 hours (approx. 2 weeks). Not until that point, the biocomposite reference panel reaches saturation at about 10 % moisture uptake, whereas the sandwich specimen mass increases continuously. After 2184 hours (13 weeks) the moisture uptake of one sandwich with 10 mm cork core is about 19 % for the first time. The assumption that the water absorption of cork sandwiches would be much higher than for the reference and standard materials, because cork is able to absorb water very well, could not be observed. Also unexpectedly, the core thickness has no significant influence on the water uptake of the bio-sandwich. The reason for this behavior could be that the cork surface is possibly sealed under pressure and high temperatures. The water is therefore mainly absorbed by the surface of the NF/PFA skin layers, which leads to a constant diffusion rate. This also explains the fact that cork has no significant influence on the water uptake until the saturation of the reference panel is reached.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

One of the main goals of this work was to expand the application area of biocomposites to structural components in order to use them as materials for the building industry. Thus, the material development as well as the investigation and optimization of the processing of biocomposites made of flax and jute textiles with PFA resin are the main focus of this paper.

Compared to standard natural fiber materials which are currently used in the automotive industry, the mechanical performance of the PFA-based biocomposites in this work could be increased tremendously. By using aligned fibers in the form of bi-directional textiles (flax – 2x2 twill, jute – plain weave) and optimizing the impregnation and compression molding process, both the stiffness and strength could be increased up to 120 % respectively 43 % compared to thermoset based standard materials. The relatively low processing temperature of 155 °C has an advantageous effect on the natural fibers, since their mechanical properties start to decrease rapidly depending on exposure time and temperatures between 170-210 °C. Both, flax and jute fibers show no decrease in mechanical performance at temperatures below 170 °C [14]. The processing temperature is also considered as main influencing factor on the emissions of NFRPC. Odor and emissions increase with increasing processing temperatures and reach an unacceptable odor and emission level when processing NFRPC above 190 °C [15]. Thus, natural fiber PFA composites have very low VOC emission [16] and are

therefore suitable for the use in the interior building sector.

Due to the expansion of cork granules at high temperatures, a hot-in hot-out process for the production of bio-sandwiches was not possible in this case. The process was adapted and the sandwiches had to be cooled in order to obtain a high quality material. As was already explained, both processes could be optimized and considerably shortened on industrial scale by using an open tool for the composites or a continuous compression molding process with heated and cooled regions for the sandwich. Also a variothermal tool could be used with high heating and cooling rates which enables a fast cooling of the sandwich materials. The effective bending stiffness of the flax/PFA composites could be increased twice by using a cork core of about 5-6 mm. For even higher requirements, the stiffness could be increased up to 800 % with a 10 mm cork core. Besides the very good stiffness, the bio-sandwich is also an excellent material for thermal insulation purposes due to the cork's low thermal conductivity [7]. Therefore, it could be used in exterior applications like external claddings.

In order to use the biocomposites and bio-sandwiches as rain-screen cladding, the water uptake was tested in a long-term experiment. The water uptake for both materials is less than 3.5 % in the first 24 hours, which is a tremendous improvement compared to standard natural fiber composites. In the first 200 hours, the cork has no significant influence on the water uptake compared to a flax/PFA reference panel. It can be assumed that the water is mainly absorbed by the surface of the composite skin layers, whereas the cork core is sealed under high pressure and temperature at the edges of the specimens.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) under grant agreement n° 285689 (BioBuild – High Performance, Economical and Sustainable Biocomposite Building Materials).

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